

KEY FACTORS AFFECTING CONSUMER PURCHASE DECISIONS IN TAOBAO LIVE STREAMING COMMERCE IN CHINA

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Abstract

Live e-commerce is an emerging shopping model in recent years. With the continuous development of live broadcast commerce around the world, live broadcast commerce has become an indispensable part of online shopping for many consumers. Social interaction is a common activity in live broadcast commerce. When there is social interaction between the anchor and consumers or between consumers and consumers, it may have an impact on consumers' purchasing decisions. This study explores how social interactions and consumer reviews of live-streaming commerce influence consumers' purchasing decisions. Based on the current development status of live broadcasting, this article sorts out and summarizes the literature that affects consumers' purchase decisions in live broadcast e-commerce from the two key factors of social interaction and consumer comments. To this end, this study draws on social influence theory and use-gratification theory and uses quantitative research methods to investigate Chinese Taobao live broadcast business users. The findings show that social interaction and consumer reviews have a positive impact on consumer purchasing decisions, and secondly, the study reveals the importance of gender as a moderating factor. Overall, this research reveals the key factors influencing Taobao live commerce purchase decision and provides useful insights to measure live commerce development strategies to provide effective advice on Taobao live commerce. Finally, the paper provides possible enlightenment for the improvement of live e-commerce.

Keywords: Live Stream Commerce, Purchasing Decisions, Social Interactions, Consumer Reviews.

1. INTRODUCTION

Live streaming commerce, also known as live shopping, is a method of online shopping that combines live video streaming with the ability to interact directly with sellers and purchase products (Huang & Benyoucef, 2013). The concept originated from television shopping channels, but the digital version offers more interactivity and immediacy (Chen et al., 2023). One of the key attractions of live streaming commerce is the interactivity it offers. Buyers can ask questions and get immediate responses, creating a more personalized shopping experience (Cheung et al., 2021). This format also builds trust, as consumers can see products in use and hear reviews in real-time (Chen et al., 2023).

In addition to the shopping aspect, live streaming commerce also serves as a form of entertainment. Many live streamers are influencers or celebrities who attract audiences with their engaging content (Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut, 2020). The sense of urgency created by flash sales and limited time offers can also encourage impulse buying (Leong, 2022). Live streaming commerce continues to grow and evolve, with western platforms like Amazon and Facebook also exploring this space (Rein & Venturini, 2018). However, it also presents challenges, including the need for regulatory oversight to prevent fraudulent practices and protect consumer rights (Ngai & Wat, 2002).

Communication and interaction social media are used to promote interaction between sellers and buyers, and between customers, and then consumers share and feedback information out of interests (Hajli & Sims, 2015; Liang & Turban, 2011). The interaction between all the parties effecting the purchase decision by identifying the perceived risk and trust. Customer trust refers to the belief and confidence that customers have in a company or brand to deliver on its promises and commitments. It is a key component of building customer loyalty and can be influenced by factors such as product quality, customer service, and corporate reputation (Jing & Xie, 2011). In survey by retail solutions provider Instamojo findings the top factors affecting customer trust in e-commerce, authenticity, professionalism, digital literacy, and payment gateways. In other research for canadine market findings the main factors affecting the trust in e-commerce trustworthiness of the internet merchant and privacy and security protection (Salehi et al., 2021).

Social interaction in the online shopping environment, often referred to as social commerce, social media platforms have increasingly been incorporated into e-commerce strategies to leverage social interaction to influence purchasing decisions (Xu & Lee, 2020). The literature finds that social interaction can heavily influence consumers' purchasing decisions (Zhen et al., 2019), Bankov (2019) found that social influences, including recommendations from peers and community members, heavily influence consumers' purchase intent in online social networking games. Social interaction in the online shopping environment greatly influences consumer trust, which in turn influences their purchasing decisions (Zhang & Gu, 2015). User-generated content, such as online reviews and ratings, has been found to significantly influence consumers' purchasing decisions in the online shopping environment (Isa et al., 2016). Social interaction in social commerce platforms significantly influences consumers' perceived value to a product, which in turn influences their purchasing decisions (Wang & Yu, 2017).

However, some research suggests that social interaction may not be the main driver of purchasing decisions (Yin et al., 2019b). According to Ribeiro et al. (2022) consumers with strong brand preferences or product-specific requirements may not be significantly affected by social interaction. Personal preferences may outweigh the influence of social interactions on purchasing decisions. Individual preferences and product-specific requirements can sometimes override the influence of social interaction (Yin et al., 2019b). In this case, consumers may rely more on their own judgment and needs than on the opinions of others. The influence of social interaction on consumers' purchasing decisions is mainly moderated by positive word-of-mouth and negative word-of-mouth factors (Wang & Yu, 2015).

In some cases, consumers who are already familiar with certain products or brands may not be significantly affected by social interaction. These consumers are more likely to make purchasing decisions based on their past experiences and personal preferences (Jian et al., 2022). In addition to this, some consumers prefer an anonymous shopping experience and do not want to engage in social interaction while shopping online. For these consumers, social interaction may not have a significant impact on their purchasing decisions (Groppe et al., 2018). Social interactions had a positive and significant effect on social presence and emotional state, but they did not have a significant effect on shopping intention (Li, 2019).

Customer reviews in e-commerce greatly influence consumers' purchasing decisions, and online customer reviews have a huge impact on customers' purchasing decisions (Chen et al., 2022; Moon et al., 2014). Customers usually seek positive and negative reviews to evaluate. For products, negative reviews can have a significant impact on consumers' purchase decisions, often causing them to reconsider or abandon a purchase (Constantinides & Holleschovsky, 2016). User-generated product reviews can significantly affect consumers' purchase intentions (Bahtar & Muda, 2016). Johan et al. (2021) found that Consumer review have a significant impact on the ranking of products online. Consumer review help to increase consumers' trust in products, thereby influencing their purchasing decisions (Guo et al., 2020). Chakraborty (2019) found that the quality of online reviews and ratings, as user-generated content, can significantly affect consumers' purchasing decisions. In addition, fake reviews tend to be more impactful than genuine online reviews.

In the e-commerce market, consumer reviews facilitate online shopping for consumers; in turn, consumers are increasingly dependent on review information to judge the quality of products and make a buying decision (Flanagin et al., 2014). Consequently, A survey conducted by Chen et al. (2022) reveals that nearly 60% of consumers browse online consumer review at least once a week and 93% of whom believe that these online reviews help them to improve the accuracy of purchase decisions, reduce the risk of loss and affect their shopping options. When it comes to e-consumers in commercial activities on business to business (B2B) and business to customer (B2C) platforms, 82% of the consumers read consumer review before making shopping choices, and 60% of them refer to comments every week. Research shows that 93% of consumers say online reviews will affect shopping choices, indicating that most consumers have the habit of reading online reviews regularly and rely on the comments for their purchasing decisions.

However, in the existing literature, findings on the role of customer reviews on customers' purchasing decisions are mixed. For example, some studies have found that consumer reviews has a positive impact on product sales (Li et al., 2019), however, other scholars believe that this relationship does not exist. In some cases, consumer review may be less effective due to various factors. For example, if consumers have a strong preference or prior experience with a brand or product, the impact of online reviews may be reduced (Cui et al., 2012). The difference in age means that their existing knowledge and experience can exceed the information in online reviews (Alhassan G. Mumuni et al., 2020; Helversen et al., 2018). Influenced by gender and mood, consumer review sometimes have an impact difference (Craciun & Moore, 2019).

1.1. Live Streaming Commerce in China

With the advancement of technology, the e-commerce industry has developed rapidly in the past 10 years (Gupta, 2014). In 2021, retail e-commerce sales amounted to approximately 5.2 trillion U.S dollars worldwide, becoming a bright spot and a new growth point of the world economic (Chevalier, 2022a), In 2022, online commerce transactions in China reached approximately RMB13.79 trillion, representing an approximately four percent year-on-year growth. The e-commerce market in China maintained a steady growth in recent years (Ma, 2023). At present, the world's leading Internet companies have built ecosystems centered on platforms. Amazon, Alibaba,

etc. take the e-commerce trading platform as the core, extend the upstream and downstream industries, and build a cloud service system(Poletti, 2018).

E-commerce originated in Europe and the United State but flourished in Asia (Shen, 2019). According to the EMarketer report, in 2020, e-commerce has become one of the fastest growing industries in the Asia-Pacific region, with digital sales approaching US\$2.992 trillion in 2021, and retail sales more than three times that of North America and nearly five times that of Western Europe E-commerce is also on the rise in Indonesia, with 73 million Indonesians spending an estimated US\$20.3 billion on online purchases throughout the year. E-commerce in Asia has a large volume and rapid development (Abrams, 2021). Among them, China's e-commerce retail transaction volume has ranked first in the world since 2013 (Cramer-Flood, 2021).

In recent years, with the development of e-commerce and the widespread application of the Internet, live streaming commerce has been growing in China, and live streaming commerce has become an important model of retail e-commerce. In China, several retail e-commerce platforms have launched live streaming e-commerce operation models, such as Taobao, Xiaohongshu (Redbook), Douyin and Kuaishou, etc., Douyin Live is a representative product in the field of live streaming. Known as TikTok outside of China, Douyin has become one of the country's leading live streaming business platforms. As of June 2020, according to the Douyin data report; There are over 600 million daily active users (Douyin, 2020).

With the surge in the number of live streaming business participants, the industry's problems are becoming more and more prominent, seriously affecting the interests of consumers, and even threatening the future development of China's live streaming business. Regulating live streaming commerce has been a challenge(Prasad Bingi & Khamalah, 2000). As livestreaming commerce grows, raises concerns about fraud, false advertising, and the sale of counterfeit or substandard products(Han et al., 2022). Regulation of live streaming businesses is still evolving(Qian & Yang, 2020). Issues include protecting consumer rights, ensuring fair competition, and preventing deceptive marketing practices. Sun et al. (2019)found that in some cases, streamers exaggerated product features or provided misleading information to boost sales. People are concerned about the quality and authenticity of the products sold through live streaming(Lu & Siegfried, 2021b). Some influencers have been found to promote counterfeit or substandard goods, undermining consumer trust(Wu & Huang, 2023).

Taobao Live is a live streaming feature of the Taobao platform that allows influencers, celebrities, and sellers to host live streams, where they showcase and sell products directly to viewers(Guo et al., 2021; Rungruangjit, 2022). Taobao Live was launched in 2016 as part of Alibaba's strategy to integrate entertainment and e-commerce(Guo et al., 2021). The feature quickly became popular due to its interactive and engaging shopping experience. Viewers can ask questions, make comments, and make purchases directly from the stream(Liu et al., 2021). Over the years, Taobao Live has introduced various features to enhance the live shopping experience, such as "See Now, Buy Now" fashion shows and virtual reality shopping(Wu & Zhou, 2017). As of 2021, Taobao Live has become Alibaba's main revenue driver. According to 2021 Taobao Live Annual New Consumption Trend Report (TLANCTR), Taobao Live's Gross Merchandise Volume (GMV) exceeded RMB400 billion (\$62 billion) in 2020 and is expected to double by the end of 2021. Taobao Live has over 800 million active users and hosts millions of live streams every day. The platform is particularly popular

among younger consumers, with a large proportion of users between the ages of 20 and 30(TLANCTR, 2021).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Background

2.1.1. Social Influence Theory

Social influence theory is a psychological concept that explains how individuals are influenced by the behaviors and attitudes of others in social networks(Turner, 1991). This theory is based on the basic human need for social interaction and the inherent human tendency to exist in social groups, a social context that influences individuals' perception of reality and thus their behavior(Tedeschi, 2017). In the context of live streaming commerce, viewers may be influenced by the behavior or comments of other viewers during live streaming (Wang & Li, 2020). If many viewers seem excited about a product or are actively buying, it may influence others to comply with this perceived positive review and make the purchase themselves. The presence of live streamers and the interaction between viewers can significantly influence consumer trust and impulsive purchasing behavior. The presence provided by live streaming platforms to viewers also influenced their purchase intent(Ming et al., 2021). Also, how viewers interact with each other and with the streamer during the live stream. These interactions can create a sense of community and camaraderie, which in turn influences the audience's purchasing decisions. For example, seeing others in an online review expressing excitement about a product, or seeing a large audience tune in to the radio, can create a form of social proof that influences viewers to also consider the product actively.

2.1.2. Uses and Gratification Theory

Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT) is an influential sociological theory (Becker, 1979; Smock et al., 2011). This theory suggests that individuals access media with different goals and play an active role in selecting information resources that they are willing to access(Liang et al., 2006). Use and Gratification Theory (UGT) is a consumer-centric theory that states that different users can use the same medium for different purposes(Severin & Tankard, 1997). This theory explains the reasons behind customers' choice of social media and the psychological needs behind their choice(Cheung & Lee, 2009). Live streaming commerce is the purchase behavior of consumers in the process of watching live entertainment(Lu & Siegfried, 2021a). Studies have shown that viewers are addicted to social media and experience a harmonious social intimacy with media(Rubin & Perse, 1987; Xiang et al., 2016). The interaction between the streamer and the audience during the live streaming narrows the psychological distance between the audience and the streamer, which can help the audience better understand the product they want, thereby increasing the audience's trust(Jiang et al., 2019). When viewers interact with streamers at live business events, it can create a sense of community (Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut, 2020). This social aspect can make the shopping experience more enjoyable, which can increase the willingness of the audience to buy in live streaming commerce.

2.2. Empirical Literature

2.2.1. Social Interaction

Social interaction refers to the process by which individuals act and respond to those around them. Essentially, it is the way people communicate, interpret, and respond to each other's words, actions, and expressions of emotion, directly or indirectly (Molet, 1972). In live streaming commerce, consumers can interact directly with streamers and other users to immediately meet the information needs needed to facilitate purchasing decisions (Cai et al., 2018; Loiacono & McCoy, 2018). Social interaction is essential to drive consumer use of live streaming (Sjöblom & Hamari, 2017). Interactivity and presence are system characteristics that should be considered, as social interaction enables smooth and effective communication among consumers (Bao et al., 2016). Communication between consumers makes online shopping more social, thereby reducing the sense of unreality (Pavlou et al., 2007). In live streaming commerce, viewers can better understand the product through interactions with other viewers. If peer reviews are positive, viewers tend to trust live streams and the products they showcase more because persuasion works better when it is made by other similar people (Lu et al., 2016). Related studies confirm that consumers' social presence can positively influence consumer trust (Ye et al., 2020), as live viewers are potential buyers of live streaming commerce, this relationship also works in live streaming commerce.

H1: Social interaction has a significantly positive relationship with purchase decision.

2.2.2. Customer Reviews

Customer review is a review or evaluation of a product or service by customers who have purchased and used it. These reviews often include ratings and written descriptions of the customer's experience with the product or service (Zhu & Zhang, 2010). The impact of consumer reviews on purchasing decisions is widely recognized. Trust in consumer reviews has proven to be a success factor in online transactions (Salo & Karjaluoto, 2007), as consumers tend to look for reliable information about products and services (Filieri et al., 2015; Filieri et al., 2018). Therefore, when reviews are received by potential customers, consumer reviews have practical significance for purchase intent, thus having a positive impact on purchasing decisions (Cox et al., 2009). Therefore, in live streaming commerce, consumers often interact to understand what other consumers are saying about a product or business to make purchasing decisions. Streaming as an online influencer is also considered a trusted source of information (Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017). In live streaming business, consumer trust can influence consumers' purchase decisions through trust in streamers, word of mouth, information quality and social networking.

H2: Customer reviews has a significantly positive relationship with purchase decision.

2.2.3. Gender

The term "gender" refers to whether a person is genetically and biologically male or female (Wilson, 2002). Gender has been considered an important research topic in different fields (Evanschitzky & Wunderlich, 2006; Hui & Wan, 2007; Krolokke & Sorensen, 2006). According to sociolinguistic theory, it has been found that gender influences communication (Krolokke & Sorensen, 2006). In spoken discourse, men

communicate to establish superior social status, while women communicate in a tone of rapport, compassion, and empathy. In the internet, where gender plays an important role in communication and e-commerce transactions (Ulbrich et al., 2011). Previous studies have also provided evidence that male and female consumers have different decision-making styles (Mokhlis & Salleh, 2009). In loyalty studies to customers, it was found that men responded more positively to status-emphasizing loyalty programs than women, but only if their higher status was very pronounced to others (Melnyk & van Osselaer, 2012).

H3: The impact of the social interaction on the purchase decision will be positively regulated by gender.

H4: The impact of the customer reviews on the purchase decision will be positively regulated by gender.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

From the literature review and critical evaluation of applied models, the study proposes that a conceptual framework was developed. This study is based on two independent variables: social interaction, customer reviews, the dependent variable is the purchase decision, and gender is the moderator variable. Through Social Influence Theory (SIT) (Turner, 1991) the influence of customer reviews on purchasing decisions can be explained. The Use and Gratification Theory (UGT) (Katz et al., 1973) strengthens the explanation of the impact of streamer attractiveness on consumer purchasing decisions.

Figure 4.1: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

To test the research model assumptions, a questionnaire was developed to conduct a web survey and collect empirical data. The items to measure each structure were largely developed from previous literature. To adapt to the live broadcast business environment, some measures have been slightly modified. We measured all these items using a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. The social interaction structure consists of 12 items. Items SI1-SI12 are from Chen and Lin (2018); Xu et al. (2020) and Hou et al. (2020) with Result of Reliability α coefficient are 0.873, 0.91, and 0.871. The consumer review structure consists of 12 items, Items CR1 to CR12 are from Singh et al. (2023); Singh and Chakrabarti (2023)

and Linlin et al. (2020) with Cronbach Alpha are 0.877, 0.944, and 0.95. This process resulted in minor revisions regarding item wording and applicability. Ultimately, the questionnaire consisted of three parts, Part A is to block questions, filter respondents through questions, and select the target respondents who meet the requirements. Part B focuses on the relevant demographics of the respondents, providing more insight into the respondents. Part C is the main part of the questionnaire, which requires the filler to fill in according to their true ideas.

3.1 Sampling and Data Collection

This study uses the services of a popular online survey website (<https://www.sojump.com/>), which is a well-known questionnaire survey website in China, to collect empirical data to test the research model. The collection time for this survey is from July 1 to July 30, 2023, and Chinese consumers with live streaming commerce purchase experience are invited to support the survey. By sending survey web pages to respondents. Once respondents receive the online questionnaire, the system automatically checks the IP address of each respondent to avoid duplication. Two masked questions were devised to identify respondents. If the answer to each question is "No", the responses are closed, and the questionnaire is considered invalid.

Distribute questionnaires through the Taobao advertising system and publish the questionnaire link on the Taobao live broadcast platform to guide users to fill in the questionnaire. Carry out targeted distribution activities, such as distribution through different live e-commerce platform forums. By setting different advertising sources, it can be ensured that users of each live broadcast platform can see the survey link. Control the number of respondents for each live platform group to ensure an appropriate sample representation for each live platform group. The motivation for the study was explained in the questionnaire and the confidentiality of the respondents' information was ensured. The questionnaire adopts attention checking methods such as repeated questions and rhetorical questions (for example, the respondent has not watched the live broadcast in the past three months, nor has he interacted with other viewers through the live broadcast), to ensure that the participants have an on-site shopping experience. If a participant answered "No" to these questions or did not provide complete answers to all questions, the questionnaire was automatically eliminated.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH RESULTS

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is an appropriate technique for analyzing empirical data in confirmatory studies (Ullman & Bentler, 2012). As a second-generation data analysis technique (Savalei & Bentler, 2006), this study applied AMOS 24.0 to examine the measurement model and the structural model by a two-stage approach of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) (Brown & Moore, 2012). Following this approach, we were able to verify the reliability, validity, and consistency of the empirical data of the measurement model and estimate the statistical significance and significance level of the path coefficients assumed in the structural model.

4.1 Measurement Properties

According to Table 4.1, all factor loadings in this study are above 0.7. Researchers also provide a rule of thumb for retaining items, and they recommend retaining items above 0.60 (Hair et al., 2014). The composite reliability values for the structures range

from 0.932 to 0.939, all exceeding the threshold of 0.7. Bagozzi and Yi (1988) and Hair et al. (2011) provide a rule of thumb for interpreting the combined reliability coefficients that a given structure should have a combined reliability coefficient value of 0.7 or above. According to Chin (1998), the extracted mean variance should be at least 0.50 or higher to indicate the convergent validity of a particular construction. AVE values ranged from 0.539 to 0.585, all exceeding the threshold of 0.5. Therefore, the results show satisfactory convergent validity. As a rule of thumb, Fornell and Larcker recommend using an AVE of 0.5 or higher. In the study, For the analysis of discriminant validity, for Social interaction, its AVE square root value is 0.742, which is greater than the maximum value of the absolute value of the correlation coefficient between factors 0.661, which means that it has good discriminant validity. For Customer reviews, its AVE square root value is 0.734, which is greater than the maximum value of the absolute value of the correlation coefficient between factors 0.584, which means it has good discriminant validity.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Construct

Construct	Item	Factor loading	Composite reliability	Mean	AVE
Social interaction	SI1	0.869	0.936	3.1678	0.550
	SI2	0.736			
	SI3	0.742			
	SI4	0.719			
	SI5	0.726			
	SI6	0.730			
	SI7	0.714			
	SI8	0.740			
	SI9	0.765			
	SI10	0.733			
	SI11	0.706			
	SI12	0.714			
Customer reviews	CR1	0.856	0.933	3.2197	0.539
	CR2	0.701			
	CR3	0.735			
	CR4	0.719			
	CR5	0.712			
	CR6	0.722			
	CR7	0.702			
	CR8	0.710			
	CR9	0.736			
	CR10	0.752			
	CR11	0.723			
	CR12	0.736			
Purchase decision	PD1	0.873	0.939	3.2379	0.585
	PD2	0.778			
	PD3	0.747			
	PD4	0.844			
	PD5	0.749			
	PD6	0.741			
	PD7	0.756			
	PD8	0.722			
	PD9	0.717			
	PD10	0.728			
	PD11	0.743			

Figure 4.2: Structural Model

As expected, all pathways proposed in the study model were supported. In other words, the Social interaction, Customer reviews and purchase decision are positively correlated. In other words, H1($\beta = 0.246$, $p < 0.001$), H2 ($\beta = 0.164$, $p < 0.001$), H3 ($t=19.329$, $\beta=0.088$, $p=0.001<0.05$), and H4 ($t=3.178$, $\beta=0.099$, $p=0.002<0.05$) are supported by Research result. And found that the attractiveness of the streamer is significantly related to the purchase decision.

Table 4.2: Model Fit Indices for the Structural Model

Index	Expected value	Actual value	Fitting results
Absolute fit index			
CMIN/DF	≤ 3	1.146	Excellent
RMR	≤ 0.08	0.053	Good
GFI	≥ 0.9	0.953	Excellent
AGFI	≥ 0.9	0.941	Excellent
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.021	Excellent
Comparative fitting indicators			
NFI	≥ 0.9	0.976	Excellent
IFI	≥ 0.9	0.943	Excellent
TLI	≥ 0.9	0.941	Excellent
CFI	≥ 0.9	0.964	Excellent
Parsimonious fitting index			
PNFI	≥ 0.5	0.824	Excellent
PCFI	≥ 0.5	0.851	Excellent

According to the test results of model fitness, it can be seen that the value of χ^2/DF (chi-square degree of freedom) is 1.146, within the range of 1-3, the RMSEA value is 0.021, and within the range of less than 0.05, the GFI 0.953 and greater than 0.9, CFI 0.964 and greater than 0.9, NFI 0.976 and greater than 0.9, TLI 0.941 and greater than 0.9, The value of IFI is 0.943 and is in the range greater than 0.9. According to the evaluation criteria of the model fitting index, in the confirmatory factor analysis model of this study, the fit indexes of CMIN/DF, NFI, IFI, TLI, CFI, GFI, RMSEA and other sub-models all meet the standard, so the CFA of this study The model has a good fit (Thompson, 2004).

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Live streaming is an important e-commerce model. In order to explore the influence mechanism of live broadcast consumers' purchase decisions, this paper studies the influence of key factors of social interaction and consumer reviews in live broadcast commerce on consumers' purchase decisions. In addition, gender was also used as a moderating variable. It provides a theoretical framework for studying the relationship between these factors. Four hypotheses are developed based on existing literature research and empirically tested using a revised supporting theoretical framework.

The findings show that social interaction has a significant impact on online consumers' purchasing decisions through live streaming commerce. A possible explanation is that social interaction plays an important role in increasing user stickiness and purchase intent on live commerce platforms (Yin et al., 2019a). The findings are consistent with previous studies that demonstrate that social interaction is a crucial factor in influencing online consumers' purchasing decisions. The results of this study are consistent with those of other surveys of social interaction and online purchasing decisions (Chen & Lin, 2018; Guangming et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2020). In addition, The specific explanation is that on the live streaming commerce platform, customer reviews are an important basis for other potential buyers to understand the quality of the product or service. Positive customer reviews can improve the credibility and reputation of a product or service, thereby increasing the purchase intention of other users (Guangming et al., 2022). The findings are consistent with previous studies that demonstrate that customer reviews are a crucial factor in influencing online consumers' purchasing decisions. The results of this study are consistent with those of other customer reviews and online purchasing decisions (Constantinides & Holleschovsky, 2016; Helversen et al., 2018; Linlin et al., 2020; Singh & Chakrabarti, 2023; Thakur, 2018).

According to the results of data empirical analysis, the results of this study are as follows: First, both social interaction and consumer review variables affect purchase decisions. Secondly, the research results found that the impact of social interaction and consumer reviews on consumer purchasing decisions is positively moderated by gender. This suggests that gender plays a crucial role in moderating the relationship between these factors and purchasing decisions. Female shoppers are more likely to be influenced by social interactions and consumer reviews when making purchasing decisions. Finally, a new live broadcast business purchase decision-making model is proposed through research. Overall, the findings support our proposed research model and yield relevant empirical observations.

The research conclusions provide important practical significance and guiding suggestions for live broadcast e-commerce platforms. This platform can strengthen the social interaction between the anchor and the audience or the audience and the audience, increase its attractiveness and trust, thereby attracting more potential buyers and improving the conversion rate of purchasing decisions. In addition, the platform can also develop corresponding strategies for consumer reviews and increase consumer review participation through points and rewards, thereby increasing the enthusiasm of the shopping experience.

5.1 Theoretical Implications

The study has two key theoretical contributions. Our first contribution to theoretical implications concerns our empirical results. This study fills a gap in the existing

literature on online consumers' live streaming of business purchasing decisions. Gain a more complete understanding of online consumer behavior. First, we explore the influencing mechanism of purchasing decisions during live streaming. Existing research shows that live streaming can drive consumer purchasing decisions. However, past studies have given limited theoretical intent.

When consumer reviews is influential, they can generate positive purchasing decisions for consumers through the influence of reviews (Chenyu & Seock, 2002). This means that customer reviews play an important social influence role in live streaming commerce, attracting and influencing consumers to make purchase decisions. Social influence theory highlights the impact of customer reviews on purchasing decisions. In summary, social influence theory (SIT) provides strong support and explanation for understanding the impact of consumer reviews on purchasing decisions. In live streaming business, consumers are often influenced by the opinions and opinions of others. The consumer reviewss can have a positive impact on purchasing decisions through social influence effects. The research results provide an important theoretical basis and practical inspiration for the live streaming commerce platform to optimize streamer selection.

Use and gratification theory posits that consumers seek to satisfy individual needs when using a particular medium or platform(Katz et al., 1973). In this study, social interaction is used as an independent variable, which represents the degree of social participation of consumers on the live commerce platform. According to the use and gratification theory, when consumers feel satisfied and enjoyable social experience, they are more likely to make purchasing decisions to satisfy social needs(Gao et al., 2023). Uses and gratification theory emphasizes the influence of social interaction on purchasing decisions(Lifu et al., 2023). In live commerce, consumers will gain satisfaction and pleasure when participating in social interaction experiences, which will affect their purchasing decisions(Ping et al., 2022).. This theory provides an important reference for the design of the live streaming commerce platform, encouraging the platform to provide a socialized shopping experience and enhancing the sense of participation of consumers.

5.2 Practical Implications

The findings of this study have several practical implications for live commerce. Social interaction has a significant impact on purchasing decisions. Therefore, the live streaming commerce platform can strengthen the social interaction with consumers and provide a more personalized service experience that is close to the needs of consumers. By actively participating in social interactions, merchants can increase consumer engagement and loyalty, and facilitate purchase decisions (Chen and Lin 2018). Both the platform manager and the host should strengthen the quasi-social relationship between the host and the audience, so that the audience will regard the host as a reliable friend and build a sense of intimacy with each other. A quasi-social interactive experience can be promoted by increasing the interaction between the streamer and the audience. Platform providers should design more social functions in the live streaming (Chen & Lin 2018), such as giving gifts (Yu et al. 2018) and more vivid real-time communication (Hu et al. 2017). Streamers should create more interesting topics to engage with viewers and reply to viewers immediately (Hilvert-Bruce et al. 2018).

In addition, consumer reviews and electronic word-of-mouth have a significant impact on purchasing decisions. Therefore, live commerce platforms can encourage users to actively participate in reviews and share positive purchase experiences, thereby increasing other consumers' trust in products and purchase motivation (Hilvert-Bruce et al. 2018). Positive consumer reviews can establish a good image for the brand and increase user loyalty and purchase intention. Consumer reviews is an important reference for other consumers to make purchase decisions. Live commerce platforms should encourage consumers to evaluate purchased products and share shopping experience. These real user reviewss can help other consumers better understand the advantages and disadvantages of products and promote consumers to make wise purchase decisions.

5.3 Limitations and Recommendation

The first limitation is the data collection process. Empirical data is primarily collected from a popular Internet survey site. All respondents were from China. This data sample may limit the generalizability of the results. Therefore, any researcher should be cautious when applying these results to other cultural and economic contexts. Future research should be devoted to exploring the business of live streaming commerceing in different countries and regions. Furthermore, cross-country comparisons are likely to yield a more comprehensive understanding and results that are more broadly applicable. Second, the study adopted a cross-sectional design, that is, the samples were investigated at the same time point. However, this design cannot determine causality, only reveals associations between variables. The data collected in the study mainly relied on self-reporting by consumers, which could lead to self-reported data bias. Consumers may have recall bias or subjective tendencies, which affect their feedback on purchase decisions and live streaming commerce experiences. In addition, gender is used as a moderating variable in the study, assuming its effect between independent and dependent variables is positive. However, gender may be only one of the influencing factors, and there are other potential moderator variables that may have an impact on the findings.

This study is limited in several ways. However, there are limitations that provide directions for future research. The limitations and future research directions are as follows: First, the samples used in the analysis were aimed at Chinese consumers, and there were more female participants than male, resulting in generalization limitations. Therefore, future research should focus on consumers in many countries. Second, although this study added gender as a moderating variable, however, gender may be only one of the influencing factors, and there are other potential moderating variables that may have an impact on the research results. Future studies can consider more moderator variables to better understand their moderating effects on influencing factors.

Researchers should try to increase the number of respondents, including some foreigners who are familiar with China's live streaming e-commerce model, to explore how cultural differences affect audiences' perceptions and usage of live streaming e-commerce. In this case, more discoveries about the future of livestreaming e-commerce in the western world will be easier to explore. Secondly, researchers should also read and think more about the literature on TV shopping, find some common points for discussion, and find out whether live streaming commerce e-commerce can produce the same or similar changes in mass consumption in different countries or

social environments. Finally, research methods should be combined to ensure the accuracy of the collected data.

References

- 1) Alhassan G. Mumuni, Kelley O'Reilly, Amy MacMillan, S., Cowley, c., & Kelley, B. (2020). Online Product Review Impact: The Relative Effects of Review Credibility and Review Relevance. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332861.2019.1700740> (159)
- 2) Bahtar, A. Z., & Muda, M. (2016). The impact of User-Generated Content (UGC) on product reviews towards online purchasing-A conceptual framework. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, 337-342.
- 3) Bankov, B. (2019). The impact of social media on video game communities and the gaming industry. *Varna: University of Economics in Varna*.
- 4) Bao, H., Li, B., Shen, J., & Hou, F. (2016). Repurchase intention in the Chinese e-marketplace: Roles of interactivity, trust and perceived effectiveness of e-commerce institutional mechanisms. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 116(8), 1759-1778.
- 5) Becker, L. B. (1979). Measurement of gratifications. *Communication research*, 6(1), 54-73.
- 6) Brown, T. A., & Moore, M. T. (2012). Confirmatory factor analysis. *Handbook of structural equation modeling*, 361, 379.
- 7) Cai, J., Wohn, D. Y., Mittal, A., & Sureshbabu, D. (2018). *Utilitarian and Hedonic Motivations for Live Streaming Shopping* Proceedings of the 2018 ACM International Conference on Interactive Experiences for TV and Online Video,
- 8) Chakraborty, U. (2019). The impact of source credible online reviews on purchase intention: The mediating roles of brand equity dimensions. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 13(2), 142-161.
- 9) Chen, C.-C., & Lin, Y.-C. (2018). What drives live-stream usage intention? The perspectives of flow, entertainment, social interaction, and endorsement. *Telematics and Informatics*, 35(1), 293-303.
- 10) Chen, H., Dou, Y., & Xiao, Y. (2023). Understanding the role of live streamers in live-streaming e-commerce. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 101266.
- 11) Chen, T., Samaranayake, P., Cen, X., Qi, M., & Lan, Y.-C. (2022). The Impact of Online Reviews on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions: Evidence From an Eye-Tracking Study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 2723.
- 12) Chenyu, J. H., & Seock, Y. (2002). Adolescents' clothing purchase motivations, information sources, and store selection criteria: a comparison of male/female and impulse/nonimpulse shoppers. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 31(1), 50-77.
- 13) Cheung, C. M., & Lee, M. K. (2009). Understanding the sustainability of a virtual community: model development and empirical test. *Journal of Information Science*, 35(3), 279-298.
- 14) Cheung, M. L., Pires, G. D., Rosenberger III, P. J., Leung, W. K., & Ting, H. (2021). Investigating the role of social media marketing on value co-creation and engagement: An empirical study in China and Hong Kong. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 29(2), 118-131.
- 15) Constantinides, E., & Holleschovsky, N. I. (2016). Impact of online product reviews on purchasing decisions. International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies,
- 16) Cox, C., Burgess, S., Sellitto, C., & Buultjens, J. (2009). The role of user-generated content in tourists' travel planning behavior. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 18(8), 743-764.
- 17) Craciun, G., & Moore, K. (2019). Credibility of negative online product reviews: Reviewer gender, reputation and emotion effects. *Computers in Human behavior*, 97, 104-115.
- 18) Cui, G., Lui, H.-K., & Guo, X. (2012). The Effect of Online Consumer Reviews on New Product Sales. *International Journal of electronic commerce*, 19. <https://doi.org/https://www.jstor.org/stable/41739503>

- 19) Djafarova, E., & Rushworth, C. (2017). Exploring the credibility of online celebrities' Instagram profiles in influencing the purchase decisions of young female users. *Computers in Human behavior*, 68, 1-7.
- 20) Evanschitzky, H., & Wunderlich, M. (2006). An examination of moderator effects in the four-stage loyalty model. *Journal of Service Research*, 8(4), 330-345.
- 21) Filieri, R., Alguezaui, S., & McLeay, F. (2015). Why do travelers trust TripAdvisor? Antecedents of trust towards consumer-generated media and its influence on recommendation adoption and word of mouth. *Tourism management*, 51, 174-185.
- 22) Filieri, R., McLeay, F., Tsui, B., & Lin, Z. (2018). Consumer perceptions of information helpfulness and determinants of purchase intention in online consumer reviews of services. *Information & Management*, 55(8), 956-970.
- 23) Flanagin, A. J., Metzger, M. J., Pure, R., Markov, A., & Hartsell, E. (2014). Mitigating risk in ecommerce transactions: perceptions of information credibility and the role of user-generated ratings in product quality and purchase intention. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 14, 1-23.
- 24) Gao, W., Jiang, N., & Guo, Q. (2023). How do virtual streamers affect purchase intention in the live streaming context? A presence perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 73, 103356.
- 25) Groppe, S., Kuhr, F., & Coskun, M. A. (2018). Anonymous shopping in the internet by separation of data. *Open Journal of Web Technologies (OJWT)*, 5(1), 14-22.
- 26) Guangming, L., Jiang, Y., & Chang, L. (2022). The Influence Mechanism of Interaction Quality in Live Streaming Shopping on Consumers' Impulsive Purchase Intention. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13.
- 27) Guo, J., Wang, X., & Wu, Y. (2020). Positive emotion bias: Role of emotional content from online customer reviews in purchase decisions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 52, 101891.
- 28) Guo, Y., Goh, K. Y., Zhang, Y., Liu, X., & Gao, B. (2021). Visual Merchandising and Selling Orientations in E-commerce Live Streaming: Evidence from Taobao Live.
- 29) Gupta, A. (2014). E-Commerce: Role of E-Commerce in today's business. *International Journal of Computing and Corporate Research*, 4(1), 1-8.
- 30) Hajli, N., & Sims, J. (2015). Social commerce: The transfer of power from sellers to buyers. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 94, 350-358.
- 31) Han, L., Zhang, Z., Li, W., & Sun, X. (2022). Game Analysis on Supervision of Quality Problems of Live Goods with Short Video Platform Participation. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 10(3), 1274-1289.
- 32) Helversen, B., Abramczuk, K., Kopeć, W., & Nielek, R. (2018). Influence of consumer reviews on online purchasing decisions in older and younger adults. *Decision Support Systems*, 113, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2018.05.006>
- 33) Hou, F., Guan, Z., Li, B., & Chong, A. Y. L. (2020). Factors influencing people's continuous watching intention and consumption intention in live streaming: Evidence from China. *Internet Research*, 30(1), 141-163.
- 34) Huang, Z., & Benyoucef, M. (2013). From e-commerce to social commerce: A close look at design features. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 12(4), 246-259.
- 35) Hui, T. K., & Wan, D. (2007). Factors affecting Internet shopping behaviour in Singapore: gender and educational issues. *International journal of consumer studies*, 31(3), 310-316.
- 36) Isa, N. F., Salleh, N. A. M., & Aziz, A. A. (2016). Determinants and impact of online social interaction on online buying behaviour. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 219, 352-358.
- 37) Jian, W., Shahzad, F., Ahmad, Z., Abdullah, M., & Hassan, N. M. (2022). Trust and consumers' purchase intention in a social commerce platform: A meta-analytic approach. *Sage Open*, 12(2), 21582440221091262.
- 38) Jiang, C., Rashid, R. M., & Wang, J. (2019). Investigating the role of social presence dimensions

- and information support on consumers' trust and shopping intentions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 51, 263-270.
- 39) Jing, X., & Xie, J. (2011). Group buying: A new mechanism for selling through social interactions. *Management science*, 57(8), 1354-1372.
 - 40) Johan, A., Rosadi, B., & Anwar, T. A. (2021). Product Ranking: Measuring Product Reviews on the Purchase Decision. *Journal of Business Studies and Management Review*, 4(2), 105-110.
 - 41) Katz, E., Blumler, J. G., & Gurevitch, M. (1973). Uses and gratifications research. *The public opinion quarterly*, 37(4), 509-523.
 - 42) Krolokke, C., & Sorensen, A. S. (2006). *Gender communication theories and analyses: From silence to performance*. Sage.
 - 43) Leong, J. Y. (2022). *A study on consumer's impulse buying behavior decision: live streaming shopping on crossborder e platform UTAR*.
 - 44) Li, C.-Y. (2019). How social commerce constructs influence customers' social shopping intention? An empirical study of a social commerce website. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 144, 282-294.
 - 45) Li, X., Wu, C., & Mai, F. (2019). The effect of online reviews on product sales: A joint sentiment-topic analysis. *Information & Management*, 56(2), 172-184.
 - 46) Liang, T.-P., Lai, H.-J., & Ku, Y.-C. (2006). Personalized content recommendation and user satisfaction: Theoretical synthesis and empirical findings. *Journal of management information systems*, 23(3), 45-70.
 - 47) Liang, T.-P., & Turban, E. (2011). Introduction to the special issue social commerce: a research framework for social commerce. *International Journal of electronic commerce*, 16(2), 5-14.
 - 48) Lifu, L., Feng, Y., & Zhao, A. (2023). An interaction–immersion model in live streaming commerce: the moderating role of streamer attractiveness. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 1-16.
 - 49) Linlin, Z., Li, H., Wang, F.-K., He, W., & Tian, Z. (2020). How online reviews affect purchase intention: a new model based on the stimulus-organism-response (SOR) framework. *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, 72(4), 463-488.
 - 50) Liu, Y., Xu, Z., Wang, H., & Xu, J. (2021). Marketing Strategy During the Pandemic: A Study of Chinese Live Streaming E-commerce Based on Taobao Live. 2021 3rd International Conference on Economic Management and Cultural Industry (ICEMCI 2021),
 - 51) Loiacono, E., & McCoy, S. (2018). When did fun become so much work. *Information Technology & People*, 31(4), 966-983. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-10-2016-0239>
 - 52) Lu, B., Fan, W., & Zhou, M. (2016). Social presence, trust, and social commerce purchase intention: An empirical research. *Computers in Human behavior*, 56, 225-237.
 - 53) Lu, Y., & Siegfried, P. (2021a). E-Commerce Live Streaming – An Emerging Industry In China And A Potential Future Trend In The World. *ACC Journal*.
 - 54) Lu, Y., & Siegfried, P. (2021b). E-commerce Live streaming–An Emerging Industry in China and A Potential Future Trend in the World. *ACC Journal*.
 - 55) Melnyk, V., & van Osselaer, S. M. J. (2012). Make me special: Gender differences in consumers' responses to loyalty programs. *Marketing letters*, 23(3), 545-559. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11002-011-9160-3>
 - 56) Ming, J., Jianqiu, Z., Bilal, M., Akram, U., & Fan, M. (2021). How social presence influences impulse buying behavior in live streaming commerce? The role of SOR theory. *International Journal of Web Information Systems*, 17(4), 300-320.
 - 57) Mokhlis, S., & Salleh, H. S. (2009). Consumer decision-making styles in Malaysia: An exploratory study of gender differences. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(4), 574-584.
 - 58) Moon, S., Park, Y., & Seog Kim, Y. (2014). The impact of text product reviews on sales. *European Journal of Marketing*, 48(11/12), 2176-2197.

- 59) Ngai, E. W., & Wat, F. (2002). A literature review and classification of electronic commerce research. *Information & Management*, 39(5), 415-429.
- 60) Pavlou, P. A., Liang, H., & Xue, Y. (2007). Understanding and mitigating uncertainty in online exchange relationships: A principal-agent perspective. *MIS quarterly*, 105-136.
- 61) Ping, X., Cui, B.-j., & Lyu, B. (2022). Influence of Streamer's Social Capital on Purchase Intention in Live Streaming E-Commerce [Original Research]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.748172>
- 62) Poletti, T. (2018). Amazon heads toward \$700 billion valuation thanks to Alexa, AWS and tax gains. *Market Watch*.
- 63) Prasad Bingi, A. M., & Khamalah, J. (2000). The challenges facing global e-commerce. *Information Systems Management*, 17(4), 22-30.
- 64) Qian, M., & Yang, H. (2020). Research on the Current Situation and Optimization Countermeasures of China's E-commerce Live Streaming.
- 65) Rein, K., & Venturini, T. (2018). Ploughing digital landscapes: How Facebook influences the evolution of live video streaming. *New media & society*, 20(9), 3359-3380.
- 66) Ribeiro, M. I., Fernandes, A. J., Lopes, I. M., & Victor, J. A. (2022). Digital Presence of Companies: Consumer Social Interaction and the Purchase Decision. In *Marketing and Smart Technologies: Proceedings of ICMarTech 2021, Volume 2* (pp. 445-457). Springer.
- 67) Rubin, A. M., & Perse, E. M. (1987). Audience activity and soap opera involvement a uses and effects investigation. *Human communication research*, 14(2), 246-268.
- 68) Rungruangjit, W. (2022). What drives Taobao live streaming commerce? The role of parasocial relationships, congruence and source credibility in Chinese consumers' purchase intentions. *Heliyon*, 8(6), e09676.
- 69) Salehi, F., Abdollahbeigi, B., & Sajjady, S. (2021). Factors affecting the trust in the online shopping and E-commerce Success of Companies. *Asian Research Journal of Current Science*, 1-5.
- 70) Salo, J., & Karjaluoto, H. (2007). A conceptual model of trust in the online environment. *Online Information Review*, 31(5), 604-621.
- 71) Savalei, V., & Bentler, P. M. (2006). Structural equation modeling. *The handbook of marketing research: Uses, misuses, and future advances*, 330, 36.
- 72) Severin, W. J., & Tankard, J. W. (1997). *Communication theories: Origins, methods, and uses in the mass media*. Longman New York.
- 73) Shen, R. (2019). The comparative history and development of E-commerce in China and the United States. 2019 3rd International Seminar on Education, Management and Social Sciences (ISEMSS 2019),
- 74) Singh, H., & Chakrabarti, S. (2023). How do gratifications to read reviews and perceived reviewers' credibility impact behavioural intentions in fashion e-commerce? A mediating-moderating perspective. *Computers in Human behavior*, 143, 107677.
- 75) Singh, H., Chakrabarti, S., & Utkarsh. (2023). How do gratifications to read reviews and perceived reviewers' credibility impact behavioural intentions in fashion e-commerce? A mediating-moderating perspective. *Computers in Human behavior*, 143, 107677. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.107677>
- 76) Sjöblom, M., & Hamari, J. (2017). Why do people watch others play video games? An empirical study on the motivations of Twitch users. *Computers in Human behavior*, 75, 985-996.
- 77) Smock, A. D., Ellison, N. B., Lampe, C., & Wohn, D. Y. (2011). Facebook as a toolkit: A uses and gratification approach to unbundling feature use. *Computers in Human behavior*, 27(6), 2322-2329.
- 78) Sun, Y., Shao, X., Li, X., Guo, Y., & Nie, K. (2019). How live streaming influences purchase intentions in social commerce: An IT affordance perspective. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 37, 100886.
- 79) Tedeschi, J. T. (2017). *The social influence processes*. Routledge.

- 80) Thakur, R. (2018). Customer engagement and online reviews. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 41, 48-59.
- 81) Thompson, B. (2004). Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis: Understanding concepts and applications. *Washington, DC, 10694(000)*.
- 82) Turner, J. C. (1991). *Social influence*. Thomson Brooks/Cole Publishing Co.
- 83) Ulbrich, F., Christensen, T., & Stankus, L. (2011). Gender-specific on-line shopping preferences. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 11, 181-199.
- 84) Ullman, J. B., & Bentler, P. M. (2012). Structural equation modeling. *Handbook of Psychology, Second Edition*, 2.
- 85) Wang, M., & Li, D. (2020). What motivates audience comments on live streaming platforms? *PloS one*, 15(4), e0231255.
- 86) Wang, Y., & Yu, C. (2015). Does social interaction affect consumer decisions on social commerce sites. *Available at SSRN 2695661*.
- 87) Wang, Y., & Yu, C. (2017). Social interaction-based consumer decision-making model in social commerce: The role of word of mouth and observational learning. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(3), 179-189.
- 88) Wilson, S. R. (2002). *Seeking and resisting compliance: Why people say what they do when trying to influence others*. Sage Publications.
- 89) Wongkitrungrueng, A., & Assarut, N. (2020). The role of live streaming in building consumer trust and engagement with social commerce sellers. *Journal of business research*, 117, 543-556.
- 90) Wu, B., & Zhou, Y. (2017). Research on influencing factors of users' continuance intention toward taobao live streaming. *E-Commer. Lett*, 6, 44-53.
- 91) Wu, Y., & Huang, H. (2023). Influence of Perceived Value on Consumers' Continuous Purchase Intention in Live-Streaming E-Commerce—Mediated by Consumer Trust. *Sustainability*, 15(5), 4432.
- 92) Xiang, L., Zheng, X., Lee, M. K., & Zhao, D. (2016). Exploring consumers' impulse buying behavior on social commerce platform: The role of parasocial interaction. *International Journal of Information Management*, 36(3), 333-347.
- 93) Xu, X., Wu, J.-H., & Li, Q. (2020). What drives consumer shopping behavior in live streaming commerce? *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 21(3), 144-167.
- 94) Xu, Y., & Lee, M. J. (2020). Understanding User Participation and Interaction in Online Shopping Communities from the Social and Relational Perspectives. HICSS,
- 95) Ye, S., Lei, S. I., Shen, H., & Xiao, H. (2020). Social presence, telepresence and customers' intention to purchase online peer-to-peer accommodation: A mediating model. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 42, 119-129.
- 96) Yin, X., Wang, H., Xia, Q., & Gu, Q. (2019a). How Social Interaction Affects Purchase Intention in Social Commerce: A Cultural Perspective. *Sustainability*, 11(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082423>
- 97) Yin, X., Wang, H., Xia, Q., & Gu, Q. (2019b). How social interaction affects purchase intention in social commerce: A cultural perspective. *Sustainability*, 11(8), 2423.
- 98) Zhang, Z., & Gu, C. (2015). Effects of consumer social interaction on trust in online group-buying contexts: An empirical study in China. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(1), 1.
- 99) Zhen, Z., Chen, M., & Zhang, W. (2019). Social community, personal involvement and psychological processes: A study of impulse buying in the online shopping carnival. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 20(4), 255-272.
- 100) Zhu, F., & Zhang, X. (2010). Impact of online consumer reviews on sales: The moderating role of product and consumer characteristics. *Journal of marketing*, 74(2), 133-148.